

OSCAR Learning and Mentoring Evaluation

Author

Dr. Scott Harrison
Postdoctoral Researcher, MCAA

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Project summary and main objectives

About the Project

Project title: OSCAR, the “Online, open learning recommendations and mentoring towards Sustainable research CAREers”

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The principal objective of OSCAR E+ Strategic Partnership was to develop, deploy and validate a personalised AI based learning, training and online mentoring service for researchers in order to support researchers, research master students and doctoral training participants in their career management and mental health awareness skills development. Therefore, the OSCAR project focused on the development of an online, AI driven open learning recommendation framework focusing on mental health and career management.

Project partners

Coordinator

TIB – Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology and University Library, Germany

Partners

USI - University of Siegen, Germany

CALP – Career & Life Planning, Ireland

RUMO, Portugal

Marie Curie Alumni Association, Belgium

SciLink Foundation, Netherlands

Associated Partner

Eurodoc – The European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, Belgium

Evaluation Overview

Evaluating the OSCAR project is an important process that helps provide feedback and reflection on the workshops successes, while also scoping areas for improvement. This evaluation implemented in OSCAR has four central objectives:

1. To understand participant needs prior to workshop deployment
2. To evaluate the design and user experience using the eDoer application within the boundaries of the mentoring workshops
3. To understand and evaluate workshop participants learning experience with respect to the mentoring workshops content and how the workshops were conducted
4. To evaluate the overall organisation of the workshops

To meet these objectives, the evaluation design is explained, covering the key methods associated with data collection. Next, the results of the evaluation design are presented, covering each of the evaluation objectives. Finally, the results are summarised, limitations are discussed, and several recommendations are made.

Evaluation Design

To meet the objectives of the evaluation, two potential designs were considered. The first was using a digital learning analytics approach, where user engagement and interaction with the eDoer platform would provide vital information on the learning process. The second option was to go with a more traditional pre/post survey, where users provided feedback using Likert scales and open ended questions. It was decided that due to the current state of development with eDoer, the second option would be best suited to the task. As such, the pre/post survey design was implemented, where the sampling unit would be the workshop participants, and the sampling frame would be all registered participants.

An important design element to the evaluation process was participant anonymity. This served a twofold purpose. On one hand it would protect participant's right to privacy during the workshops. On the other hand, this would help encourage participants to provide open, objective critical feedback necessary for project organisers and mentors to improve the workshop process. As such, the surveys avoided linking any information which may have identified participants or facilitated reidentification.

Two surveys are constructed on the Qualtrics platform, using a combination of yes/no questions, likert scale sliders, short answer questions and open ended questions. Both the pre-workshop and post workshop survey is designed to start with a consent question where they have to explicitly opt-in to have their data collected. Participants are also provided with all the necessary information regarding the data collection process, the intent of how their data will be processed, and who to contact should they wish to review or retract their data.

Results

The results of the evaluation covers four key areas, the pre-workshop survey, eDoer, workshop conduct and content, and workshop implementation. For the pre-workshop survey, there were 69 respondents in total, while for the post-workshop survey there were a total of 17 respondents.

Pre-workshop Survey

The main objective with the pre-workshop survey was to attain a rudimentary understanding of the participants registering for the two workshops. For the first workshop, we had 35 responses to the survey, while for the second workshop we had 34 responses, giving a total of 69 for both workshops overall. It's important to note that we also differentiate between registrants and participants. As to be expected, we had a number of people who registered for the workshops who for reasons could not participate on the day. So in the pre-workshop survey we refer to people as registrants, while in the latter post-workshop surveys, they are referred to as participants.

The first question asked of registrants was with respect to age, to provide a basic indicator of where people may be at in their life and career journeys. Figure 1 provides a breakdown of the age of workshop participants by age classes, as well as by the two workshops.

Figure 1. Distribution of workshop registrants by age

From Figure 1, we can ascertain that most of the people registering for the OSCAR workshops are aged between 26 and 45, with only a few people in workshop 1 and 2 being outside this age range. This also indicates that early career researcher status aligns with age, however this is not strictly always the case, as it's plausible for people to become researchers after already having a career in another occupation.

The second key demographic question related to gender, where registrants were given multiple options to choose from. The breakdown of registrants by gender and workshop is provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Workshop registrants by gender and workshop

From Figure 2, we observe that the majority of registrants identified as female. The distribution of genders between the two workshops was relatively similar. Given the target audience and also gender distributions in academia in general, this was not in line with our expectations, and this is discussed in greater detail when summarising the workshop findings.

The next question asked to workshop registrants was with respect to caring responsibilities. The objective of this question was to ascertain what extra stresses may be affecting people’s mental health and career options outside of the immediate workplace. The results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Registrant caring responsibilities by workshop

The results show that most participants have no caring responsibilities in both workshops, however there are a number of registrants who do have children to take care of. Interestingly, we noted that this was more pronounced in workshop 1 compared to workshop 2.

Finally, we asked registrants their status as an international mobile researcher. Registrants were provided with a working definition of this term, that being ‘an international is a researcher who is currently working outside of the country they normally reside in’. The breakdown of responses are provided in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Registrants by international mobile researcher status

The results showed us that there was a much larger proportion of registrants in workshop 2 that identified as international mobile researchers when compared to workshop 1 registrants. As such, this information was used to help inform the workshop mentors as to potential issues that may arise given participants' mobile situation.

Beyond these found key demographic questions, participants were also asked to rate their satisfaction with various dimensions of their life. The four key areas that we asked registrants to rate were their career trajectory, work environment, family life, and social life. Participants were given a slider option in Qualtrics to indicate their level of satisfaction, ranging from extremely dissatisfied on the left, to extremely satisfied on the right. The slider responses were then coded onto a 100 point scale, with extreme dissatisfaction coded to 0, and extreme satisfaction coded to 100. In total, both workshop 1 and 2 had 30 respondents each to this section of the survey. For easy comparison of the distribution of responses, a box and whisker plot is used where the four metrics are shown for both workshop 1 (W1) and workshop (W2) in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Satisfaction of workshop participants with respects to four key life dimensions (0 = extremely dissatisfied, 100 = extremely satisfied)

Starting with career trajectory, we can see that the median value for workshop 1 is around 65, indicating a moderate level of satisfaction. In workshop 2 however, the median value is lower, indicating a lower level of satisfaction overall with respect to career trajectory. The plots between workshop 1 and 2 are very similar with respect to the quartile distributions and minimum and maximum values.

With respect to work environment satisfaction, we see a greater difference in the distribution of responses between workshop 1 and workshop 2. In workshop 1, the median value is close to 50, indicating neither satisfied or dissatisfied with their work environment. However, looking at the second quartile, shaded in light grey, we can see that the responses for workshop 1 range from somewhat dissatisfied to neither. However, in workshop 2, not only is the median value higher indicating a higher level of satisfaction, but that the bottom of the second quartile is close to the median value of workshop 1. This indicates that the cohort of registrants for workshop 1 and 2 have a difference in work environment satisfaction, and that this difference needed to be accounted for in delivering the training materials for the workshops.

This difference between the two workshops continued into the next metric, family life satisfaction. The median value for workshop 1 was around 70, indicating that at least 50% of registrants were somewhat satisfied or more with their family life. This was the highest observed median value for the survey with respect to these measures. Workshop 2 however showed a

much greater variation in responses, and a lower median value of 60. The second quartile responses indicate that a number of registrants were somewhat dissatisfied with their family life. This again provides important information for the workshop mentors of potential challenges and issues that may arise during the workshop conduct.

A similar pattern was also observed when asked about social life satisfaction. Registrants for workshop 1 showed a higher level of satisfaction, with a median value of 60, and a second quartile distribution starting at 50. This indicates overall that the majority of people registered in workshop 1 were somewhat satisfied with their social life. However, in workshop 2 we see a much greater dispersion of responses again. The median value for workshop 2 was 50, and the second quartile of responses started at 20, which is between somewhat dissatisfied and extremely dissatisfied.

In summary, the pre-workshop survey was able to elicit some key differences between registrants for workshop 1 and 2 which can be used to inform the conduct of the workshops themselves to meet the needs of the registrants.

eDoer

Evaluating eDoer as an application was essential to understanding the influence of the learning platform on the workshop outcomes. To evaluate the participants' experience using the application, questions were asked on how much they agreed with six key statements. The results are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Evaluation of eDoer (0 = strongly disagree, 100 = strongly agree)

With respect to navigation, we can see that overall, most participants agree that the application was easy to navigate and utilise. Furthermore, most participants agreed that the application instructions were clear and easily understood. The learning topics selected met the needs of most participants, and that the learning modules themselves provided helpful information.

When asked if they would recommend the eDoer application to others, we see a larger dispersion of agreement. Despite the increased dispersion, the bottom of the 2nd quartile indicates that at least 75% of workshop participants would agree to recommending eDoer to others. This result indicates that in the context of the workshops, the eDoer application fulfilled the requirements for the workshops as a platform.

An important component to the evaluation process however was also providing space for participants to answer open ended questions. Three questions were asked of participants, where they could provide open text responses. These were: *“Did eDoer provide you content that aligned with your learning needs? Were there any issues or bugs that you came across when using the application? Do you have any recommendations on how we can improve the eDoer application?”*

There were only limited responses to these questions so no detailed analysis was performed on the feedback to extrapolate clusters or trends, however, the feedback was passed onto the eDoer developers to help improve the dimensions of the application that certain users had issues with.

Workshop Content and Conduct

With respect to the workshop content and conduct, participants were asked again how much they agreed with a set of six statements, with a value of 0 corresponding to strongly disagreeing with a statement, and 100 indicating that they strongly agreed with the statement. Given the limited number of participants in each workshop, the results are presented separately for the mental health and career mentoring sessions, but amalgamated the data from workshop 1 and 2. Doing so ensured that there were 9 responses to the questions on mental health, and 8 responses to the questions on career planning. The results are presented in Figures 7 and 8 respectively.

Figure 7. Workshop evaluation for the mental health sessions
(0 = strongly disagree, 100 = strongly agree)

For the mental health workshops, we find that overall there was a high level of support for the sessions fostering a positive experience. The dispersion of responses is close to the median value of around 90, and indicates a strong level of support of the mentor’s capacity to run the workshops. There is a greater dispersion of agreement when asked if the amount of communication with the workshop mentor was sufficient, however, there is still a high level of agreement with the statement, with a median value above 90. When asked about the level of communication between participants, we see a high median of 97, however we also see a greater dispersion in the responses in the second quartile. This indicates that the experience may have been strongly positive for a number of participants in their ability to communicate with others, but it wasn’t universal.

When asked whether they developed a sense of connection with their mentors, this elicited the most diverse response from participants. The median value was above 80, indicating that at least 50% of participants agreed with the statement, however, the second quartile indicates that some participants were ambivalent about this, and the minimum value indicates that for at least one person, they disagreed with the statement. This warrants deeper investigation, with some ideas being proposed in the conclusions of this report to this point.

Asked if participants developed a sense of connection with peers, the second and third quartiles are very tightly grouped around the median value of 78. While this is a lower median than the

previous item, the minimum value indicates that at worst, a participant neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement.

Finally, participants were whether the workshop process was sensitive to their situation and that it gave them a sense of confidentiality. This question was important in evaluating the level of discretion and support that could be given to workshop participants, especially when dealing with the sensitive topic of mental health. The results indicate that the majority of participants agreed or strongly agreed. This is an important result as it shows that in the context of OSCAR, the topics of researcher mental health can be addressed in an appropriate and supportive manner.

Figure 8. Workshop evaluation of the careers planning sessions (0 = strongly disagree, 100 = strongly agree)

When looking at the workshop results for career planning, the results show a similar level of agreeance (or higher) across the battery of six questions presented in Figure 8. For the six questions, the median value is 80 and 95, indicating that they agree or strongly agree with the positive statements. Furthermore, the dispersion of results is relatively narrow across the scales, which indicates a consistent level of agreeance from all participants. The only noteworthy minimum was on the item regarding whether the process was sensitive to their situation and giving a sense of confidentiality. However, given this was the minimum and it neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement, we can conclude that overall, the workshops for career planning met participants needs and were conducted in a manner that was supportive of their learning needs.

Workshop Implementation and Outcomes

The last dimension of evaluation was with respect to the overall implementation of the workshops and the impact they had on workshop participants. The first two questions relate to the registration process, followed by three questions on the workshop topics, and a final question asking participants how likely they are to recommend the workshops to others. The results are presented in Figure 9.

Overall, 75% of participants either agreed or strongly agreed that the registration process was relatively easy to navigate. This is important as it indicates that there was no artificial barrier to registering for the workshops which would potentially exclude people. For the one participant who disagreed with this statement, their feedback was carefully analysed and incorporated into the workshop process. This was also similar in the agreement with the statement for the registration information being clear and informative. The majority of people agreed with this statement, with a median value of around 87, however, where a participant disagreed with this statement, their feedback was carefully incorporated into improving the processes for future workshops. The majority of participants agreed or strongly agreed that the topics covered were relevant to their situations.

With respect to the workshops improving participants' understanding of mental health, we see a wider dispersion of results, with the bottom of the second quartile starting at 59 and the upper part of quartile three finishing at 93. From this we can interpret that participants had a wider range of experiences during the workshops with regards to mental health, and that while the responses are majority positive, there is some scope to improve how the mental health component of the workshops are run. One confounding reason for this that consistently came through the open feedback options was the availability of time for the mentoring sessions.

Figure 9: Workshop implementation and outcomes
(0 = strongly disagree, 100 = strongly agree)

With respect to the career planning workshops, we see a tighter dispersion of responses in quartile two and three, indicating that most participants agreed that the workshops improved their understanding. We also note that there was one 0 response for this item, however upon further investigation this appears to be an invalid response as the participant failed to use the slider for the item.

Finally, when asked if the participants would recommend the OSCAR workshops to others, the response was overwhelmingly positive, and this was supported through the open feedback options that participants could reply with.

The open questions at the end of the survey allowed for any recommendations or feedback to be supplied. Again, due to the limited number of participant responses (n=17), there was little scope to provide a deep analysis of the responses. However, all information was passed on to the relevant project partners to ensure that they could improve their processes where needed.

Summary of Findings

The results indicate that there was a difference in the two workshops with respect to the participants registering for the event. In the second workshop, we observed that there were more international mobile researchers registering. Furthermore, we found that participants in the second workshop were more satisfied with their work life, yet simultaneously, more dissatisfied with their family and social life. To this end, there is scope to further investigate if there is a link between international mobile researchers and where they are satisfied with different aspects of their lives, and how much does the mobility of their research position impact on these dimensions.

A second interesting finding was that there was a larger dispersion of responses (relative to other responses) when asked about the level of connection participants felt to the mental health mentors. The responses are likely to have been impacted and affected by a number of limiting factors associated with the workshops, mainly time and the mode of delivery. A consistent theme in the open feedback that participants provided was that the sessions weren't long enough both for the eDoer learning component in the morning, but also for the mentoring sessions in the afternoon. Additionally, the online format of the workshops is going to have an impact on the level of connectivity one can feel with a mentor.

These form two of the key limitations to the conduct of the workshops. Another key limitation to the evaluation process overall is the limited sample size of responses. While there was a relatively large sample ($n > 30$) for the registration pre-workshop survey, the number of people who participated in both workshops combined was a lot less than 30. As such, a key limitation that needs to be kept in mind when interpreting the results of the post-workshop survey is that this may not be overly representative.

With that in mind, we have found that overall, the OSCAR workshops have provided an excellent start to improving both researcher mental health and career planning through the use of the eDoer platform. Given the general positive findings from the post-workshop survey, it would be recommended to expand on the workshop format to be available on a more frequent basis to provide better ongoing support, while also looking to expand the impact of the workshops by increasing the depth of the learning experience by provisioning more time for the sessions.